

Research Article

Understanding User Satisfaction in Business Performance During the COVID 19 Outbreak (Tik Tok Application Users in Indonesia)

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Abstract

This study understands the social media platform TikTok that drives user satisfaction to improve business performance during the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. Running a business using social media can make it possible to promote a product or service in a variety of ways. They will be able to adopt a particular social networking platform if it can fulfill their business goals. This study used 150 samples of Indonesian student data using an online questionnaire. Furthermore, the analytical method used is Pearson correlation and regression. The findings of this study reveal that user satisfaction with TikTok social media has led to customer engagement, personal branding, and promotion. Marketers can adopt social media applications that can provide a level of satisfaction using these applications in improving their business performance.

Keywords: Business performance, user satisfaction, Tik Tok

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic that has afflicted the majority of countries has fundamentally impacted entrepreneurial financing (Howell, Lerner, Nanda & Townsend, 2020). For example, during the issuing of a Movement Control Order, fast-food establishments such as KFC, McDonald's, and Subway experienced a shift in demand and income (Kee, Mohd Nazr, et al., 2021). This has a financial and economic impact on Starbucks because it has shaken the global economy, especially the food and beverage industries (Sinha, 2021). Follow the mainstream by inventing, understanding product qualities, and customer preferences if entrepreneurs want consumers to be interested in local products and build purchasing power (Anwar, 2018). As a result, the correct digitization strategy is critical for achieving company objectives and developing products or services that are more competitive (Fitriasari, 2020). On the other hand, businesses are starting to formulate business performance to inspire their thinking (Mejri, MacVaugh & Tsagdis, 2018). Mejri (2018) says that the application of relevant knowledge in companies is beneficial for product output, innovation and orientation of active commodity markets, and sustainable business development. While COVID-19 threatens businesses of all sizes, social networks are offering new tools designed expressly to assist small enterprises in surviving the epidemic. Facebook, for example, has announced shops, a new tool that will allow retailers to exhibit and sell their products on the network. The move comes as many shops were forced to close their physical storefronts due to the COVID-19 outbreak, and many are now eager to sell online. Meanwhile, Instagram has introduced a new feature to assist small companies in making sales, this time in the form of gift cards, meal orders, and fundraiser stickers that can be shared through Stories.

TikTok is another video creation software that has grown in popularity, according to Mullery (2021). When individuals are unable to travel, TikTok has become an excellent platform for businesses and customers to trade and share their lives by posting short interactive videos. It enables users to create, share, and respond to short-form music video content.

TikTok users have utilized the program to share audio samples of their dancing, acting, and exercising videos with their pals. Users can also watch other people's videos by using thumbs or bookmarks. Mullery (2021) further said that TikTok is the second most downloaded iPhone app in 2020 with serves to capture the imagination of people and organizations regardless of age, location, or gender. Furthermore, TikTok's algorithm selects which types of content are exposed to various types of viewers. From a brand view point, early entry into the TikTok market can be uncharted ground. Most brands would never consider this, yet the TikTok platform is seeing a significant increase in popularity. TikTok's new brands are frequently the major creators of it. These content makers are professionals at creating viral material that will help them achieve a large number of views by exposing their business to one of the most appealing economically engaged groups. Branded campaigns with influencers are frequently one of the most straightforward ways for entrepreneurs to get involved on TikTok. When it comes to developing TikTok content, many entrepreneurs don't know where to begin; partnering with influencers is a wonderful way to get started. (Jeffries, 2020).

The ability to sell and buy items on the platform is a major concern for consumers and businesses. Customers may examine things from all over the world and enjoy favorable prices without leaving their homes thanks to this method of selling and buying products via live streaming. Businesses may save money on rent, PR, advertising, and other expenses, and TikTok gives tools for merchants to self-serve advertising. As a result of this app, an increasing number of businesses are selling through TikTok (TikTok algorithm for, 2020). As a response, the site is gaining 250 million unique users per day, with up to 500 million people active each month. This is because this app gives a big number of customers to merchants. Merchants can gain manufacturer collaboration through negotiations with Taobao, Tmall, Jingdong, and other platforms, and immediately hang their commodity links in the commodity window of their TikTok for consumers to purchase (TikTok for business, 2020). Even though the impact of COVID-19 on small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) is insufficient, it is obvious that they are nonetheless affected by the crisis. (Doshi et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2018;

Yerramilli et al., 2018). According to Razavi and AbAziz (2017), SMEs make up a major share of the population in developing countries. Doshi et al. (2018) revealed that before the COVID-19 boom, e-commerce had already begun to take off by giving an effective way to sell products to specific poor countries or enterprises with weak markets. In the short term, e-commerce has improved today's developing countries' sales issues; however, in the long term, this developing country has directly profited from the development of e-commerce. Social media, in addition to e-commerce and internet technology, is utilized to help SMEs grow. As globalization progresses, they have more opportunities to grow, and the size of SMEs grows (Razavi & AbAziz, 2017). This view point is supported by Ha, Khapova, and Lysova (2018), who claim that SMEs are more adaptable, flexible, and innovative, making them better suited for e-commerce. Evidence of e-commerce trends during the COVID-19 pandemic is presented in Kee, Nasser et al. (2021), when Pos Malaysia couriers had to work overtime even during the pandemic due to increasing demand, so many packages had to be sent to clients. Several companies have recognized the value of the TikTok platform and are using it to sell their products. Chipotle, a fast-food restaurant, is currently filming food promotions, running competitions for TikTok users, and submitting funny videos at their locations, according to Brandastic (2020). The National Basketball Association (NBA) and National Football League (NFL) released highlight game cameos via TikTok.

TikTok took a while, but the platform eventually introduced official channels for brands to advertise. For example, TopView Ads are videos that appear as soon as the user opens the app, In-Feed Native Ads are videos that appear in the users' feed as they scroll, Branded Hashtag Challenges are videos that inspire users to form submissions using a specific hashtag, Branded Effects are impact filters to use during a video to feature brand-specific information, and Brand Takeover is full-screen static or dynamic display ads that capture views (Flores, 2020). The purpose of this research is to explore how social media platforms, particularly Tik Tok, assist in the improvement of company performance during the COVID-19 epidemic. The researcher wishes to reveal how Tik Tok provides satisfaction to consumer consumers,

causing them to continue using TikTok, thus improving the company's performance. During the COVID-19 epidemic, social media has evolved as one of the most effective marketing tools for improving business performance.

Moreover, The diminishing volume of various commercial transactions is one of the causes of the economy's recession and slowness. There are several types of businesses that are surviving and growing during the COVID-19 pandemic, such as MSMEs that shift production to health products such as masks and hand sanitizers. This is considered in line with efforts to gain a competitive advantage through product innovation and market needs and wants dynamics (Taufik A, Esti H, 2018). Various forms of business engagement can benefit from various innovations. Interaction in the business world can take the form of a B2B (Business to Business) model where business transactions occur between business people and other business people, B2C (Business to Consumer) business interactions that are carried out by producers to consumers directly, C2C (Consumer to Consumer) business interactions that are carried out by individuals (consumers) to other individuals (consumers), C2B (Consumer to Business) business interactions that are carried out by an individual to other individuals (Sandhusen, R. 2008).

Furthermore, the use of physical or social separation during COVID-19 has consequences for the transition of traditional commercial activities to the internet (Patma, Wardana, Wibowo & Narmaditya, 2020). The pandemic is compelling SME managers to use free social media since they are conscious of the costs during this crisis state, allowing managers to immediately reach their customers (Effendi, Sugandini & Istanto, 2020). Social media is a low-cost technology that allows SMEs to engage with their customers at a low cost. He, and Zhang (2019). According to Aifuw et al. (2020), the COVID-19 epidemic has a negative relationship with the financial and non-financial performance of private Nigerian enterprises. Hidayati and Yansi (2020) discovered a drop in demand for goods and services on MSME sales in Jakarta. Because social media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, and WhatsApp are generally accessible to everyone, they take advantage of this opportunity by selling things via

social media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, and WhatsApp. Furthermore, this method is seen as low-cost and straightforward, which develops confidence between manufacturers and customers. This enables them to observe real-time products being sold on social media channels, along with constructive feedback or testimonials. Likewise, the International Labour Organization (ILO) revealed in 2020 that more than 60% of the surveyed firms reported insufficient cash flow to pay expenses such as employee salaries and other company expenses. MSMEs in Indonesia were also significantly damaged by the COVID-19 epidemic, thus to overcome the challenge, MSMEs were broadening their sales or marketing channels through the use of social media (Syaifulah, Syaifudin, Sukendar, & Junaedi 2021). Syaifulah et al. (2021) also found that using social media for marketing has improved MSMEs' sales, customer connections, productivity, and innovation.

Li et al. (2020) revealed that social media plays a vital role in distributing information such as government and industry policies, allowing entrepreneurs to be more aware of policy alterations that have a significant impact on business performance. Yasa et al. (2020) stated that social media has permeated every level of society and every facet of human activity. As a result, it assists business owners in reaching their target market, communicating their products, and maintaining positive client connections. Furthermore, adopting social media as a marketing tool assists business owners in establishing marketing competencies such as market sensing and customer connection, both of which can have an impact on business performance (Tarsakoo & Peerayuth, 2019). The quality of social media content has a significant impact on business performance; judgments on consistent active presence should be made platform by the platform to help promote client involvement on social media (Tafesse & Wien, 2018). It also assists businesses in raising awareness and improving client relationships (Pourkhani, Abdipour, Baher, & Moslehpour, 2019). Furthermore, social media marketing efforts have a substantial impact on brand recognition, brand image, and brand loyalty. A structural equation model was used to demonstrate this (Bilgin, 2018). Companies have seen that using social media has

enhanced brand awareness and image. Gutierrez, Ugalde, and Radhakrishnan (2019). According to Radhakrishnan and Ugalde (2019), despite the disadvantages, there are benefits to consider, such as corporations adopting social media to give clear messaging and ensure online imagery reflects their brand image.

Mohammedhussen and Abdulnasir (2019) emphasize the primary advantages of social media in business. According to the findings of a study on the role of social media marketing in value co-creation and engagement among smartphone users in China and Hong Kong, social media marketing is effective in fostering value co-creation, engagement, repurchase, and future behavior (Cheung, Pires, Rosenberger, Leung, & Ting, 2020). During the COVID-19 pandemic, Susanto et al. (2021) investigated the interaction between social media and business. In this study, 67 percent of respondents stated that the use of social media had improved their business in terms of cost-effectiveness and overall performance improvement as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic. Businesses may quickly gather input from clients through social media, which helps them enhance their business performance. Meanwhile, Xu, Yan, and Zhang (2019) analyzed TikTok as their subject to determine how this social media app grew famous. It was due to the variety of marketing promotion strategies. TikTok's popularity was aided by its advertising marketing and numerous offline and online activities to broaden the communication venue, in addition to the star promotion of exploiting the celebrity effect. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that TikTok has a substantial impact on successfully reaching its target audience through generating sales through TikTok (Azpeitia, 2021).

According to Weiss (Su, Baker, Doyle, & Yan, 2020), the TikTok app attracted 12 million US users in March 2020 and a total of 52.2 million global users, making it the most downloaded non-gaming app on the Apple app store in the first quarter of 2020. TikTok is exploding due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which has kept most people at home. One of TikTok's unique algorithm features is that if a user watches a video in its entirety, it is more likely to appear in other users' feeds than if they merely watch for a brief amount of

time. Furthermore, it gives good editing skills, allowing users to employ video editing elements such as accessible filters, stickers, effects, and music to make promotional films (Memon, 2020). As a result, we

have developed three hypotheses to investigate throughout our conversation (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Research Framework

H1: There is a positive relationship between user satisfaction from using social media on customer engagement.

H2: There is a positive relationship between user satisfaction from using social media on personal branding.

The law of reciprocity is a social standard that requires one positive activity to be followed by another positive action (Memon, 2020). For example, if a user likes, comments on, and shares another user's post, it encourages other users to do the same for that user.

Mullery (2020) also stated that posting videos when our followers are most active would assist our video building engagement with other people in a short period. This enhances the likelihood of our films being exposed to more users. Personal branding is the deliberate process of building, positioning, and sustaining a favorable image of oneself based on one's distinctive particular traits, which ensures audiences (Gorbatov, Khapofa, & Lysova, 2018). TikTok gives users access to Followers' Activity, which lets them arrange the timing of their posts. It is expected that if a user is satisfied with this function, he or she would continue to use the app and eventually develop a strong personal brand.

Mullery (2021) stated that TikTok is a community and that assisting others can go a long way toward helping each other. According to McGlew (2021), a common question a social media user may ask is whether they need a huge number of followers to become viral or get clients. TikTok users, on the other hand, have a chance for their videos to appear on the "For You Page" even if they only have a few followers. The TikTok application necessitates the regular posting of high-quality material (Riley, 2021). TikTok's algorithm gives a high degree of pleasure to users since it requires fewer efforts to interact with clients because it provides all of the necessary functionalities and help. This pleasure encourages users to continue using TikTok and posting content regularly, resulting in effective engagement with potential consumers.

H3: There is a positive relationship between user satisfaction from using social media on promotion. Relevant hashtags, trending music, etc. allow videos to get featured and gain more likes and followers. Widen (2020) mentioned that the more TikTok videos are created and posted, the more the possibility of the videos to get into FYP or "For You Page", the first

feed someone gets to see right after opening the app. TikTok videos that are generated and posted, the more likely they are to appear on the FYP which is the first feed that someone sees after opening the app. Instagram, too, offers a similar option, notably the Instagram Explore Page (Widen, 2020). Why would someone use the app if they were dissatisfied with it? Users of social media are more likely to be satisfied if they feel it is simple and worthwhile to devote their time to a particular app. Several literature studies and facts have previously been presented to counter the benefits of Tik Tok in making it easier for users' intentions to manage their business. As a result, Tik Tok gives a high degree of pleasure, allowing people to keep using Tik Tok.

Sample and procedure

Research Method

The distribution of a Google form containing 22 questions was given to students at several universities in Indonesia, namely UNIB, UNSRI, UI, and UNPAD. Random participants to explore how social media, especially Tik Tok, helps business performance during the COVID-19 pandemic. Respondents totaling 150 samples were used to perform the analysis. In addition, we managed to collect data on the behavior of respondents in the use of social media (Tik Tok). This set consists of 5 items that ask about their personal experience of using Tik Tok daily.

Measures

The researcher used a four-section questionnaire that included demographic information, personal

experience, happiness with Tik Tok usage, and the impact on business performance. Except for the demographic information, all sections used a 5-point Likert scale. We asked respondents to rate their level of agreement with each statement (1=strongly disagree; 5=strongly agree). Part 1 (demographic information) has six items that allow respondents to provide personal information such as gender, age, race, nationality, occupation, and entrepreneurship. Part 2 (personal experience with Tik Tok) includes 5 questions about the Tik Tok application's user experience, such as whether they have installed the application, how long they have been using it, and so on. Part 3 (impact of satisfaction using Tik Tok) has 5 things that raise concerns about the impact of Tik Tok and its impact on user behavior. Part 4 (effect on business performance) assesses the impact on business performance as a result of the Tik Tok application's satisfaction. This component included six questions, two for each variable: customer engagement, personal branding, and promotion. The descriptive analysis, Pearson correlation, and regression analysis were all performed in parts 3, 4.

Results

The number of respondents is 150 users of the Tik Tok application in Indonesia with most of them aged between 21 and 23 (69 and 40 percent), the majority are women (72 percent) with those surveyed being entrepreneurs or small business owners, product agents, shippers, or resellers.

Figure 2. Descriptive Analysis of Respondents' Demography (N = 150)

Figure 3,4,5,6 shows the summary of the data of respondent personal experience using TikTok

Figure 3. The purpose of Tik tok users

Figure 4. Tik tok users on smartphones

Figure 5. Tik tok for product promotion

Figure 6. Type of use tik tok

Figure 7. Time duration using Tik Tok

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics, Cronbach's Coefficients Alpha, Zero-Order Correlations of All Variables

Variables	1	2	3	4
1. User satisfaction	0.894			
2. Customer Engagement	0.645**	0.847		
3. Personal Branding	0.663**	0.510**	0.858	
4. Promotion	0.657**	0.685**	0.526**	0.678
M	4.12	3.78	4.11	3.95
SD	0.77	0.90	0.80	0.82

Note: N = 100; *p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001. Diagonal entries in bold indicate Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha; M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation.

Table 1 represents the descriptive statistics, Cronbach alpha, and correlations for all variables in the study. Variables 2–3 contained two items each, whereas the first variable (user satisfaction) contained five items, and all of the items in all four variables were given in the questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale. The Cronbach alpha for user satisfaction (= 0.894), customer engagement (= 0.847), and personal branding (= 0.858) all indicate a significant relationship between the collection of elements in each category, with values ranging from 0.8 to 0.9. Meanwhile, the Cronbach alpha for successful promotion (= 0.678) suggests that the association between the collection of elements inside this component is strong enough to be accepted, with a value close to 0.7. Moreover, the correlation coefficient for all of the relationships is positive. In fact, coefficients ranging from 0.510 to 0.685 suggest a substantial positive association between the variables. These positive numbers indicate that when the value of one variable rises, the value of another rises as well. To begin, the coefficient value (= 0.510) indicates that customer engagement and personal branding have a moderately good association. Customers engage more actively with intriguing, innovative, and transformative information and experiences, according to Tafesse & Wien (2017). For example, on Tik Tok, users can create movies based on a trending hashtag, music, and video effect, allowing them to communicate with customers on a more personal level and reply to their comments and

inquiries, thereby increasing customer engagement. When consumer interaction rises, customers will be able to construct their brand unconsciously, which is why it's called personal branding.

The coefficient value (= 0.685) indicates that consumer involvement and promotion have a stronger relationship. TikTok produces a popularity wave by engaging with targeted audiences through the use of trending hashtags, music, and effects. It means that a big number of people will see and react to the videos, especially if they are advertisement-like or soft-selling marketing videos. This method explains how consumer interaction leads to a successful promotion. A person's brand is the unique combination of talents and experiences that define who they are and what they do (Geysler, 2020). Through deliberate self-marketing and self-promotion, effective personal branding distinguishes oneself from other professionals in their area. You can get most consumers to like, engage, and provide their opinions if you have a strong personal brand. Satisfied customers will not only continue to support the business but will also help to market it to others. Furthermore, they may often boost various promotion activities on brand pages to raise engagement and audience size. As a whole, it can be argued that personal branding and effective promotion have a considerable beneficial relationship.

Table 2. Summary of Regression Analysis

Customer Engagement		Personal Branding		Promotion	
Variable entered	Beta	Variable entered	Beta	Variable entered	Beta
$(R^2 \text{ Changes} = 0.417)$ Satisfaction		$(R^2 \text{ Changes} = 0.441)$ Satisfaction		$(R^2 \text{ Changes} = 0.432)$ Satisfaction	
	0.646**		0.664**		0.658**

Note: N = 100; *p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001

As shown in Table 2 user satisfaction was used as the independent variable to examine the relationships between customer engagement, personal branding, and effective promotion. As a result, The results of the regression analysis showed that testing the three hypotheses showed that H1, H2, and H3 were acceptable. Tik Tok user satisfaction has a relationship with all three dimensions of business

success (customer interaction, personal branding, and promotion).

Discussion

The first hypothesis (H1) states that there is a link between customer engagement and satisfaction with social media (Tik Tok). The score of 0.646** indicates that the satisfaction of users has a substantial impact on the process of engaging with consumers and targeted

audiences. Unlike other social media platforms, TikTok does not necessitate the creation of an audience beforehand. The video will automatically speed up the pace in the algorithm if you create original stuff. Users must first be happy with the tools provided to create short, fashionable, and interesting videos to market their brand before they may create content. Indeed, every effect, such as hashtags, music, and filters, aids users in getting their video to show in other people's feeds, increasing engagement with the target audiences.

Many people were reportedly forced to work from home because they were unable to travel to work unless the job allowed them to do so directly. As a result, social media has served as a platform for them to carry out their duties, notably in the realm of online business. Hypothesis (H1) is accepted. The second hypothesis (H2) was created to show that there is a link between user satisfaction with social media (TikTok) and personal branding. The result of 0.664** indicated that TikTok users' contentment had a considerable impact on their branding. Since the epidemic caused chaos in the economy, some brands and even businesses have gone bankrupt as a result of the loss of business.

Meanwhile, TikTok gives company owners a way to construct, manage, and re-build personal branding. In comparison to other social media platforms, TikTok quickly grows a significant audience. TikTok offers users to select download and duet options, letting videos be shared indefinitely across all social media platforms. The nicest aspect about TikTok is that non-followers can contact businesses using TikTok's capabilities. A business owner, for example, may have posted a packing video and mentioned the buyer in it. The buyer can then download the video and share it with their contacts on other social media platforms including WhatsApp, Instagram, and Facebook. When more potential buyers become interested in the product, they will begin to follow, contact, and interact with the company. As a result, the second hypothesis (H2) is confirmed.

The third hypothesis (H3) states that there is a link between user happiness with social media (TikTok) and effective promotion. The score of 0.658** indicates that the user's pleasure with TikTok has a

considerable impact on the promotion. In the case that TikTok's algorithm differs from those of other social media platforms, TikTok inadvertently functions as a promotion tool when users learn to enjoy the happiness they get from using the app regularly, without the users having to work hard for it. Regarding examples for promotion, we've heard of direct selling, radio, and personal approach. However, TikTok users are not obligated to do so; in fact, doing so may result in their videos being shadow-banned. The only effort TikTok users must make is to create unique content and add some additional effects, all of which are provided by TikTok. The next thing we know, the videos are showing up in a lot of people's feeds, which we call "effortless promotion." As a result, the third hypothesis has been accepted. Overall, the findings and debate show that while social media does not have an impact on business performance, users should be content with the services and features that are accessible.

Conclusion

This sense of fulfillment encourages users to use social media regularly, while also improving the process by which users carry out their commercial tasks, resulting in enhanced business performance. This feature is critical in the current circumstances in Indonesia, where e-commerce is rapidly growing. According to the findings of this research, TikTok user satisfaction is highly related to all three dimensions of business performance (customer engagement, personal branding, and effective promotion). As a result, it has been established that social media aids company performance during the COVID-19 epidemic. Shortly after the COVID-19 pandemic broke out, the number of social media users skyrocketed, owing to travel limitations. TikTok has also grown significantly, with 500 million monthly active users and 250 million daily unique users. Users are urged to use social media as a tool to improve overall business performance, based on the favorable conclusion reached in the analysis of the results and the huge growth in the usage of social media.

Most importantly, TikTok's contentment has encouraged consumers to use the app regularly, resulting in improved business performance. According to the data, TikTok is beginning to acquire

traction in Indonesia as a marketing tool for promoting products and services. Social networking is the way of the future for advertising one's brand or business. The trend of video marketing isn't going away anytime soon. According to research, 85 percent of respondents want to see more videos from brands. According to research, more than 67 percent of users are considering using TikTok to promote their brand, therefore there is a lot of space for development in the number of user subscribers who will use TikTok for commercial purposes. During the coronavirus, the app's reach and engagement increased due to a surge in new users who aren't in the traditional teenager demographic. In conclusion, entrepreneurs can use TikTok as a publicity tool to gain client interaction. TikTok can also be used as a marketing tool to help people build their brands. The significance of social media in business has never been greater. The results revealed how important social media marketing has become since the COVID-19 pandemic. Because a pandemic is a worldwide occurrence, these findings are likely to be applicable in a variety of countries.

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